

Recommendation 23:

Social Media & Social Networking

Participate access to public sector services (political participation)

Using 'Social Media & Social Networking' to meet the societal need 'Participate access to public sector services (political participation)'

Status quo:

Today as many as 152 countries out of 193 (four out of five; in Europe 39 out of 43) offer social networking features, such as the "Like" button, on their national portals (i.e. there are links to, for example, Facebook, Twitter, Sina Weibo (in China), Odnoklassniki/VK in the Russian-speaking countries, etc.)

For example in the UK 100% of the local governments use twitter, 90% Facebook, 68% YouTube, 54% Flickr and 38% Instagram.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- Social media are very popular in Europe. Currently there are 412 million active users in Europe and 39 out of 43 European countries offer social networking features in their national portals.
- There are no real technological challenges, as social media services are already provided by big companies (e.g. Facebook, twitter). Current challenges persist in other areas like e.g. cyber security or issues regarding privacy and data protection.

Non-technical challenges:

- *Training*: the public sector needs personnel with the necessary digital literacy and the capacity to deal with the inputs received via social media services
- *Commitment*: to actively engage citizens via social media
- *Promotion*: the public sector organizations have to promote their social media presence
- *Cyber security* and also privacy and data protection issues are important and have to be dealt with
- *Regulations*: governments and local administrations should set up social media strategies including e.g. privacy requirements, acceptable and forbidden content, data handling, citizen engagement, etc.

Participative access to public sector services (political participation):

Our informants mentioned establishing trust in governance, voicing their opinions, accessing timely and accurate information, unlinking public sector and politics as some of the key needs under this header.

One informant expressed his opinion as: "A clear point of authority to be established (often have to roam offices because it is not clear the authority for a particular task)."

Social Media and social networking:

*Social Networking refers to the act of establishing online many-to-many human connections for the purposes of sharing information with the network or subsets thereof, and is based on computer-mediated technologies that make up an online environment allowing the creation, consumption, promotion, distribution, discovery, and sharing of content (e.g. information, ideas, career interests and other forms of expression) via virtual communities and networks. The common features of social networking applications or social media are that they are interactive web 2.0 internet based applications, involving the creation of service-specific user profiles and leveraging user-generated content, and facilitating the development of online social networks. Essentially, social media are web-based services that allow individuals to construct a public or semi-public profile within a bounded system, articulate a list of other users with whom they share a connection, and view and traverse their list of connections and those made by others within the system.**

*Gartner IT Glossary Social networking. <http://www.gartner.com/it-glossary/social-networking/>. Accessed 14 August 2017.
Gartner IT Glossary Social Media. <http://www.gartner.com/it-glossary/social-media/>. Accessed 14 August 2017.
Wikipedia Social media. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Social_media. Accessed 14 August 2017.